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Öğretmen Adaylarının Web 2.0 Araçlarına İlişkin Farkındalık ve Kullanım Yetkinliklerinin Öğretim Uygulamalarına Yönelik İnançlarını Yordamadaki Rolü

The Role of Pre-service Teachers' Awareness and Usage Competence of Web 2.0 Tools in Predicting Their Beliefs Towards Teaching Practices

ÖZET

Dijital teknolojiler ve Web 2.0 araçları, eğitim ortamlarında aktif katılımı, etkileşimi ve özerkliği artırmaktadır. Bu süreçlerin öğretim ortamlarına etkili entegrasyonu için öğretmen adaylarının Web 2.0 araçlarına yönelik farkındalık ve kullanım yetkinliklerinin geliştirilmesi kritik önem taşımaktadır. Bu noktada araştırmanın amacı, farklı disiplinlerden gelen öğretmen adaylarının Web 2.0 araçlarına ilişkin farkındalıkları ile bu araçları kullanmaya yönelik becerileri arasındaki ilişkiyi incelemek ve bu değişkenlerin öğretmen adaylarının gelecekteki öğretimlerinde Web 2.0 araçlarını uygulamaya yönelik inançlarını yordamadaki rolünü belirlemektir. Araştırmanın yöntemi ilişkisel tarama modelidir. Öğretmen adaylarının Web 2.0 araçlarına yönelik farkındalıkları ve kullanım yetkinlikleri araştırmanın bağımsız değişkenlerini, Web 2.0 araçları ile ileriki öğretmenlik yaşantılarında etkili öğrenme tasarımı gerçekleştirebilme inançları ise bağımlı değişkenini oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada bağımsız değişkenler arasındaki ilişki korelasyon analizi ile, bağımsız değişkenlerin bağımlı değişkeni ne doğrulukta yordadığı ise lojistik regresyon analizi ile incelenmiştir. Çalışmanın örneklemini lisans ve formasyon eğitimi alan 195 öğretmen adayı oluşturmaktadır. Veri toplama aracı olarak “Web 2.0 Araçlarına Yönelik Farkındalık Ölçeği (WAYFÖ)” ve “Web 2.0 Araçları Kullanım Yetkinliği Ölçeği (WAKYÖ)” kullanılmıştır. Analiz sonuçları WAKYÖ ile WAYFÖ'nün alt boyutları arasında pozitif yönde ve anlamlı ilişkiler olduğunu göstermiştir. Yapılan lojistik regresyon analizinde öğretmen adaylarının Web 2.0 araçlarına ilişkin farkındalıklarının ve bu araçları kullanma yetkinliklerinin öğretimlerindeki uygulamalarına yönelik inançlarını yordadığı tespit edilmiştir. Araştırmanın sonunda ise ileride gerçekleştirilecek olan çalışmalar için öneriler bulunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Web 2.0 araçları, Farkındalık, Web 2.0 kullanım yetkinliği, Lojistik regresyon, Öğretmen adayı

ABSTRACT

Digital technologies and Web 2.0 tools significantly enhance active participation, interaction, and learner autonomy within educational environments. For the effective integration of these processes into instructional settings, it is critical to foster the awareness and proficiency of pre-service teachers regarding the use of Web 2.0 tools. Accordingly, the aim of this study is to examine the relationship between pre-service teachers' awareness of Web 2.0 tools and their skills in using these tools, and to determine the role of these variables in predicting pre-service teachers' beliefs about implementing Web 2.0 tools in their future teaching practices. The study employed a correlational survey model. Pre-service teachers' awareness of Web 2.0 tools and their competence in using these tools constituted the independent variables of the study, while their beliefs about their ability to design effective learning activities using Web 2.0 tools in their future teaching practices constituted the dependent variable. In the study, the relationship between the independent variables was examined through correlation analysis, whereas the extent to which the independent variables predicted the dependent variable was analyzed using logistic regression analysis. The sample of the study consisted of 195 pre-service teachers enrolled in undergraduate and pedagogical formation programs. The data were collected using the “Awareness Scale for Web 2.0 Tools (ASWT)” and the “Web 2.0 Tools Usage Competence Scale (WTUCS)”. The results of the analysis indicated that there were positive and significant relationships between WTUCS and the sub-dimensions of ASWT. Furthermore, the results of the logistic regression analysis revealed that pre-service teachers' awareness of Web 2.0 tools and their competence in using these tools significantly predicted their beliefs about implementing Web 2.0 tools in their teaching practices. Finally, several recommendations for future studies were presented based on the findings of the study.

Keywords: Web 2.0 tools, Awareness, Web 2.0 usage competence, Logistic regression, Pre-service teachers

1. INTRODUCTION

The integration of technology into education has long been a focal point for educators seeking to enhance the quality of teaching and learning. Over time, advances in digital technology have transformed the way knowledge is created, shared, and experienced in educational settings. Among these developments, the emergence of Web 2.0 technologies has marked a turning point, transforming the internet from a static information repository into an interactive and participatory learning environment (Gillmor, 2004; O'Reilly, 2007). Unlike Web 1.0, which primarily allowed users to consume information, Web 2.0 enables users to generate, modify, and disseminate digital content collaboratively (Alexander, 2006). This shift has not only altered online communication and social interaction but has also opened new pathways for collaborative learning, peer feedback, and collective knowledge construction in education (Alexander, 2006; Brown & Adler, 2008; Churchill, 2011; Downes, 2005; Richardson, 2010; Thompson, 2007).

Web 2.0 technologies such as blogs, wikis, social networking sites, and video-sharing platforms are now recognized as tools that promote active participation, interactivity, and learner autonomy. These platforms support the creation of virtual learning communities where individuals can exchange ideas, construct knowledge together, and engage in authentic communication that extends beyond traditional classroom boundaries (Bonk, 2009; Brown & Adler, 2008; Butler, 2012; Downes, 2005). A key feature of Web 2.0 tools is their free and open accessibility, which enables continuous learning beyond traditional classroom limits (Solomon & Schrum, 2007). The participatory nature of these environments aligns well with contemporary learning theories that emphasize constructivism, collaboration, and learner-centered approaches. In addition, Web 2.0 tools facilitate the development of essential twenty-first-century competencies such as critical thinking, creativity, and digital literacy by encouraging students to become not just consumers but also producers of information (Albion, 2008; Discipio, 2008; Greenhow, 2007; Pascopella, 2008).

The growing reliance on digital technologies in education has demonstrated that, in extraordinary circumstances such as global crises or disruptions, the ability to sustain learning through online and digital environments is essential. These experiences have underscored the importance of digitalization, distance education, and the effective use of web-based tools, emphasizing the need for both teachers and students to develop strong digital competencies (Geçgel et al., 2020). Teachers play a crucial role in ensuring the continuity and quality of education through digital networks and platforms (Çelik, 2021). Therefore, it has become increasingly evident that teachers must possess not only technological awareness but also the pedagogical ability to integrate Web 2.0 tools effectively into their subject areas. In this sense, digital competence has become a fundamental component of professional preparedness, enabling teachers to create engaging and adaptive learning environments in both face-to-face and online contexts.

Despite their educational potential, studies have shown that the mere availability of technology does not guarantee effective pedagogical integration. Numerous studies emphasize that teachers' beliefs, awareness, self-efficacy, and technological competence play a central role in determining how and to what extent these tools are used for teaching purposes (Bullock, 2004; Choy et al., 2009; Dexter & Riedel, 2003; Ertmer, 2005; Teo, 2009; Wright & Wilson, 2006). As noted by Tagg (2003), the integration of educational technologies into teaching can either reinforce traditional teacher-centered approaches or promote more interactive, student-centered environments, depending on how these technologies are employed in instructional design. In this regard, pre-service teachers represent a critical group, as their attitudes and competencies toward technology during teacher education programs significantly shape their future teaching practices. Prensky (2001) suggests that current pre-service teachers, who belong to the generation he previously defined as 'digital natives,' use technology with natural ease in line with this definition. However, the study indicates that this familiarity is generally limited to personal or social use rather than pedagogical applications. Regardless of whether they are digital natives, pre-service teachers need to develop a comprehensive understanding of technology, content knowledge, and pedagogy, as well as how these elements interact to support effective teaching (Mishra & Koehler, 2006; Zhao & Frank, 2003). Lei (2009) emphasizes that being tech-savvy in daily life does not equip pre-service teachers with the necessary pedagogical skills or confidence to integrate digital tools into teaching contexts effectively. This gap highlights the need for targeted preparation and guided experience within teacher education programs to help bridge the divide between technological familiarity and classroom application. Previous studies suggest that while pre-service teachers are generally comfortable with using technology, this familiarity does not always ensure their pedagogical competence in integrating it effectively into classroom practice (Baltacı-Göktalay & Özdilek, 2010; Coutinho, 2008; Duan et al., 2024; Lei, 2009; Momdjian et al., 2025; Sadaf et al., 2016). Empirical findings from various contexts further emphasize this discrepancy, particularly highlighting that while pre-

service teachers may be generally comfortable using technology, this does not automatically translate into effective pedagogical integration. Duan et al. (2024) found that intrinsic beliefs strongly influenced pre-service teachers' intentions to integrate technology, with some teachers still exhibiting reservations despite high familiarity. Similarly, Momdjian et al. (2025) investigated the effectiveness of different approaches for developing digital competence among pre-service teachers in Lebanese teacher education programs. Using a mixed-methods design, the study compared direct instruction, integrated approaches, and teacher modeling. Results highlighted the need for authentic learning experiences, reflective practices, and guided modeling to strengthen digital competence across all domains.

Given the increasing prevalence of Web 2.0 tools in education, recent studies have specifically examined pre-service teachers' perceptions and use of these technologies. For instance, Baltacı-Göktalay and Özdilek (2010) investigated Turkish pre-service science and computer teachers' perceptions of Web 2.0 tools. They found that while their attitudes and acceptance levels toward these technologies were generally positive, their actual classroom use was restricted to a few familiar tools such as instant messaging, video sharing, and social networking. Tools that require content creation and collaboration, such as wikis or blogs, were used far less frequently. This suggests that, although pre-service teachers recognize the value of Web 2.0 tools for enhancing interaction and learning, they may lack the pedagogical or technical readiness to integrate them effectively into instructional design. Complementary evidence from Sadaf et al. (2016) provides a broader theoretical perspective. Drawing upon the Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior, their research identified key factors that predict pre-service teachers' intentions and actual use of Web 2.0 tools. Their findings revealed that perceived usefulness, self-efficacy, and student expectations were the strongest predictors of pre-service teachers' willingness to use Web 2.0 tools in their future classrooms. Moreover, these factors were found to have a significant influence on the translation of intention into practice during student teaching experiences. Pre-service teachers who perceived Web 2.0 tools as valuable for student engagement and learning, who felt confident in their ability to use them, and who received support from mentor teachers and students were more likely to integrate such tools into their teaching. Conversely, those who encountered barriers such as limited access to technological resources or unsupportive school environments struggled to implement their intentions in practice.

These studies underscore that the integration of Web 2.0 tools is not merely a technical challenge, but a pedagogical and psychological process shaped by teachers' awareness, perceived competence, and beliefs about the value and usefulness of these tools. Teachers' attitudes toward technology, self-assessed skills, and perceived relevance of Web 2.0 tools to learning outcomes directly influence their motivation and confidence to employ them effectively. At the same time, contextual factors—such as access to resources, institutional support, and mentor modeling—either facilitate or constrain the translation of digital intentions into actual classroom practice (Bullock, 2004; Choy et al., 2009; Wright & Wilson, 2006).

Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2010) assert that pre-service teachers' self-efficacy and capacity to establish collaborative learning environments may be enhanced by granting them the opportunity to participate in hands-on experiences with Web 2.0 tools, develop technology-enhanced lesson plans, and observe or reflect on effective integration models. These findings highlight the need to develop awareness and competence in utilizing Web 2.0 technologies for pedagogical purposes within teacher education programs. Moreover, incorporating reflective practice and evidence-based strategies into teacher education curricula can help bridge the gap between technological familiarity and instructional application. In this context, it is becoming increasingly critical to comprehend the manner in which pre-service teachers perceive their competencies and awareness of Web 2.0 tools, and how these perceptions are relevant to their beliefs about incorporating them into future classrooms. Investigating these relationships can provide valuable insights into their readiness to adopt technology-supported teaching, contributing to the design of teacher education programs that foster the meaningful, sustainable, and evidence-based integration of digital technologies into pedagogy. The growing emphasis on twenty-first-century skills and digital transformation in education makes it essential to explore how pre-service teachers conceptualize, value, and intend to apply Web 2.0 tools as future educators responsible for guiding the next generation of learners in technology-rich learning environments. However, there is limited empirical evidence examining how pre-service teachers perceived competencies and awareness of Web 2.0 tools interact to predict their actual intentions to use these tools in future teaching contexts.

The purpose of this study is to determine the competencies of pre-service teachers from different disciplines in using Web 2.0 tools, their levels of awareness regarding these tools, and the relationship between these variables. Furthermore, logistic regression analysis was conducted to examine the extent to which awareness

and competence levels predict pre-service teachers' likelihood of using Web 2.0 tools in their future teaching practices.

2. METHOD

This study utilised the correlational survey model. Survey research is a study approach used to identify individuals' tendencies and attitudes based on data obtained from a specific sample group (Creswell, 2014). In the correlational survey design, one of the types of survey research, researchers aim to examine the possible relationships between variables of interest through statistical analysis methods such as correlation or regression, without intervening in the process of the study (Goodwin & Goodwin, 2016). In this study, pre-service teachers' awareness and competence in using Web 2.0 tools were treated as independent variables, whereas their beliefs about their ability to implement effective instructional design using Web 2.0 tools in their future teaching careers were treated as the dependent variable. Correlation analysis was used to analyze the relationship between the independent variables, and logistic regression analysis was used to assess the accuracy with which the independent variables predicted the dependent variable. The main purpose of logistic regression analysis is to predict the probability of individuals belonging to a particular group by establishing a regression model. This analysis is employed in the social sciences to construct a meaningful and valid model by outlining the relationship between dependent and independent variables, aiming for best fit with minimal variables, corresponding to other statistical modeling techniques (French et al., 2013). Logistic regression (LR) studies attempt to predict a dichotomous dependent variable from a set of independent factors. Predictor variables in the LR model can be continuous, dichotomous, categorical, or any combination of the above (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). In this study, pre-service teachers' beliefs about their ability to implement effective instructional design using Web 2.0 tools in their future teaching careers is a dichotomous dependent variable.

2.1. The Sample of the Study

The sample consisted of 195 pre-service teachers enrolled in undergraduate and pedagogical formation programs at the faculty of education of a state university in Türkiye. The criterion sampling method is used to determine the sample for the study. The criterion sampling method involves studying all cases that meet a set of criteria and is also a purposive sampling method. Criteria can be developed by the researcher, or a pre-existing list of criteria can be used (Marshall & Rossman, 2014). The fundamental concept in this sampling method is the examination of all cases that meet a pre-determined set of criteria (Grix, 2019). In this study, the criterion identified was that pre-service teachers had taken a course in Instructional Technologies during their undergraduate education and pedagogical formation training. Descriptive findings regarding the sample group's gender, age, and academic program are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of the Sample Group According to Demographic Characteristics

Demographic Variable	Groups	N	%
Gender	Female	141	72.3
	Male	54	27.7
Age	18-20	43	22.1
	21-23	89	45.6
	24-26	30	15.4
	27-29	9	4.6
	30 and higher	24	12.3
Departments of Pre-service Teachers	Chemistry	73	37.5
	Mathematics	30	15.4
	Sociology	17	8.7
	Philosophy	17	8.7
	Physics	10	5.1
	Biology	10	5.1
	English language	8	4.1
	Turkish language	6	3.1
	Pre-school	3	1.5
	Music	3	1.0
	Art	2	1.0
	Computer	2	1.0
	Family Education and Counselling	2	1.0
	German language	1	0.5
	Educational Sciences	1	0.5
	French language	1	0.5
	Primary school	1	0.5
History	1	0.5	

When examining the findings in Table 1, it was observed that 72.3% of the sample group were female and 27.7% were male. When the age distribution of the sample group was analysed, it was determined that the highest proportion (45.6%) was among pre-service teachers in the 21–23 age group. This was followed by sample aged 18–20 (22.1%), those aged 24–26 (15.4%), those aged 30 and above (12.3%), and those aged 27–29 (4.6%). When the sample distribution by departments was studied, the largest group was the field of Chemistry, accounting for 37.5%. This was followed by Mathematics with 15.4%, Sociology and Philosophy with 8.7%, and Physics and Biology with 5.1%. English Language represented by 4.1%. Participation rates in other departments were 3.1% and below.

2.2. Data Collection Process and Tools

In this study, the ‘Awareness Scale for Web 2.0 Tools (ASWT)’ and the ‘Web 2.0 Tools Usage Competence Scale (WTUCS)’ were used to determine the awareness and competence levels of pre-service teachers taking the Instructional Technologies course regarding Web 2.0 tools. Also, additional data was collected through a personal information form to reveal the pre-service teachers' knowledge and views regarding Web 2.0. Before participants began using the data collecting tool, they were verbally informed of the study's aim, the necessity of voluntary participation, their right to withdraw from the study at any time, and the study's potential risks and benefits. Participants responded to the data collecting tool after declaring that they were taking part voluntarily. The data collection tools were administered to participants face-to-face, and responses were collected directly via paper forms.

2.2.1. Personal Information Form

A personal information form consisting of five questions was prepared by researchers to determine pre-service teachers' knowledge and thoughts about Web 2.0 and was used in the data collection process. The statements in the form were structured as half-sentences, and participants were asked to choose one of the two options provided to complete these statements. The questions in the form are discussed in detail in the findings section.

2.2.2. Awareness Scale for Web 2.0 Tools (ASWT)

ASWT is used to measure the awareness levels of pre-service teachers taking Instructional Technologies course regarding Web 2.0 tools. Developed by Arslan and Arı (2021), ASWT consists of the sub-dimensions of ‘knowing,’ ‘perception,’ and ‘emotion’. The scale is a 5-point Likert-type scale ranked as follows: “Strongly disagree (1), Disagree (2), Undecided (3), Agree (4), and Strongly agree (5).” Arslan and Arı (2021) conducted reliability and construct validity analyses of the scale, which has content and face validity, online with 310 volunteer secondary school students. The scale consists of 27 items, and the factor loadings for the scale items range from 0.824 to 0.386. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient is 0.926 for the “knowing” factor, 0.902 for the “perception” factor, and 0.780 for the “emotion” factor. The Cronbach's alpha value for the scale as a whole is 0.929. The minimum score that can be obtained from the scale is 27, and the maximum score is 135.

2.2.3. Web 2.0 Tools Usage Competence Scale (WTUCS)

WTUCS is used to measure the competence levels of pre-service teachers taking the Instructional Technologies course in relation to Web 2.0 tools. Developed by Çelik (2021), WTUCS consists of a single sub-dimension. The scale is a 5-point Likert type, with ratings of 'Never (1), Rarely (2), Occasionally (3), Often (4), and Always (5)'. Çelik (2021) first conducted reliability and construct validity analyses of the scale, which has content and face validity, using exploratory factor analysis with 409 teachers and pre-service teachers in face-to-face interviews and confirmatory factor analysis with 338 teachers and pre-service teachers. The scale consists of 39 items, and the factor loadings for the scale items range from 0.84 to 0.46. The Cronbach's alpha value for the scale as a whole is 0.98. The minimum score that can be obtained from the scale is 39, and the maximum score is 195.

2.3. Data Analysis

IBM SPSS v.24, a statistical package programme for social sciences, was used to analyse the quantitative data of the research. Before examining the relationship between pre-service teachers' awareness of Web 2.0 tools and their competence in using them, the normality of the data was tested. Due to the number of participants being greater than 50 (N=195), the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test results were examined to determine whether the data obtained from ASWT and WTUCS showed a normal distribution. Subsequently, a Pearson product-moment correlation analysis was performed to explain the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the scores obtained from the ASWT and WTUCS. Prior to the Pearson

product-moment correlation coefficient analysis, fundamental assumptions such as whether the data exhibited a normal distribution, the existence of a linear relationship between variables, and the effect of outliers were examined and found to be met (George & Mallery, 2022; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Cohen's (1992) effect size classification was used to interpret the correlation values (r) obtained in the correlation analysis. According to this classification, an absolute correlation value in the range of 0.00 – 0.29 indicates a low effect size, in the range of 0.30 – 0.49 indicates a medium effect size, and 0.50 and above indicates a high effect size.

3. FINDINGS

The findings section presented data acquired from the pre-service teachers' personal information forms using descriptive statistics. The results of the ASWT and WTUCS were then presented, and a correlation study between the scores from these two scales was carried out. Furthermore, a logistic regression analysis was performed to identify the variables that predict pre-service teachers' beliefs about conducting effective learning activities using Web 2.0 tools.

3.1. Findings from the Personal Information Form

The distribution of responses provided by pre-service teachers taking the Instructional Technologies course is presented in Table 2. The results showed that 42.1% of pre-service teachers said they had previously taken the Instructional Technologies course, while 57.9% said they were doing it for the first time. 43.6% of pre-service teachers said they had no prior teaching experience with Web 2.0 tools, compared to 56.4% who said they had. Similarly, it was found that 55.9% of pre-service teachers were knowledgeable of Web 2.0 tools, compared to 44.1% who were not. 36.4% of pre-service teachers actively used Web 2.0 tools, whereas 63.6% had never used them previously and reported using them for the first time in this course. Additionally, 92.3% of pre-service teachers said they believed they could successfully incorporate Web 2.0 resources into their teaching methods.

Overall, the findings indicated that a significant proportion of pre-service teachers, despite their limited prior knowledge and experience with Web 2.0 tools, had high confidence in their ability to use these tools to implement effective learning activities in their future teaching practices.

Table 2. Findings from the Personal Information Form

	N	%	
In my previous education,	I took the Instructional Technologies course.	82	42.1
	I am taking the Instructional Technologies course for the first time.	113	57.9
In my previous education,	I had knowledge about Web 2.0.	110	56.4
	I did not have knowledge about Web 2.0.	85	43.6
In my previous education,	I had knowledge of Web 2.0 tools.	109	55.9
	I did not have knowledge of Web 2.0 tools.	86	44.1
In my previous education,	I actively used Web 2.0 tools.	71	36.4
	I did not use Web 2.0 tools. I learned to use them for the first time in this course.	124	63.6
...I can use Web 2.0 tools effectively in my teaching practice.	I believe that	180	92.3
	I do not believe that	15	7.7

3.2. Correlation Analysis Findings for WTUCS and ASWT

Before conducting the correlation analysis of WTUCS and ASWT and its subdimensions, the data were examined to determine whether they were normally distributed. According to the results of the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, the data were found to meet the assumption of normal distribution ($p > .05$). Accordingly, Pearson Correlation Analysis was conducted to determine the relationships between the variables. Table 3 displays the findings of the correlation analysis.

Table 3. Findings of the Correlation Analysis of the WTUCS and ASWT

		ASWT	WTUCS	ASWT- Knowledge	ASWT- Perception	ASWT- Emotion
ASWT	r	1				
	p					
	N	195				
WTUCS	r	.490**	1			
	p	.000				
	N	195	195			
ASWT- Knowing	r	.842**	.465**	1		
	p	.000	.000			
	N	195	195	195		
ASWT- Perception	r	.836**	.382**	.569**	1	
	p	.000	.000	.000		
	N	195	195	195	195	
ASWT- Emotion	r	.712**	.381**	.471**	.607**	1
	p	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	195	195	195	195	195

**The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

Examining Table 3 revealed positive and significant correlations ($p < .01$) between ASWT and the WTUCS as well as between the *knowledge*, *perception*, and *emotion* sub-dimensions of ASWT and WTUCS. Among the sub-dimensions, the strongest correlation with WTUCS was observed for the *knowledge* dimension, followed by the *perception* and *emotion* dimensions, respectively. The correlation between ASWT and WTUCS scores was found to be moderate and positive ($r = .490$, $p < .01$). These findings indicate that pre-service teachers with higher levels of awareness of Web 2.0 tools tend to demonstrate higher levels of competence in using these tools within the Instructional Technologies course. WTUCS showed positive correlations with all ASWT sub-dimensions, with the strongest relationship observed for the knowledge sub-dimension. Overall, the findings suggest that higher levels of awareness are associated with higher levels of competence in utilizing Web 2.0 tools.

As the correlation analysis revealed a significant relationship between pre-service teachers' awareness and competence in using Web 2.0 tools, logistic regression analysis was conducted to determine the predictive effect of these variables on the pre-service teachers' beliefs about performing effective learning activities with Web 2.0 tools. Given the high correlations observed among the ASWT sub-dimensions, the possibility of multicollinearity was considered; therefore, only the total scores of the ASWT and WTUCS were included in the logistic regression analysis.

3.3. Findings of a Logistic Regression Analysis on the Belief Variable Regarding the Application of Web 2.0 Tools

Prior to conducting the logistic regression analysis of the belief variable concerning the effective implementation of Web 2.0 tools, model-based research hypotheses were established. The hypotheses are presented as follows:

H1: ASWT scores impact beliefs on how to use Web 2.0 tools effectively.

H2: WTUCS scores impact beliefs on how to use Web 2.0 tools effectively.

The investigation began with an examination of the model's initial state. For this reason, the dependent variable's baseline condition was evaluated using Block 0 analysis. Block 0 (Beginning Block) represents the initial state of the model before the awareness variable was included. The results of the Block 0 analysis are presented in Table 4. At the Block 0 stage, the -2 Log Likelihood value of the initial model, which included only the constant term, was calculated as 105.764. This value indicates the model's initial fit.

Table 4. Block 0 Test Results

		-2 Log Likelihood	Constant (β_0) values
Block 0	1	116,671	1.692
	2	106,317	2.291
	3	105,767	2.470
	4	105.764	2.485
	5	105.764	2.485

When the omnibus test results were examined, it was observed that the developed model was meaningful and that the added variables improved the model at a statistically significant level ($p < .05$). This result showed that the awareness and usage competence variables significantly and accurately predicted pre-service teachers' beliefs about implementing Web 2.0 tools in their future teaching practices. The model summary results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Model Coefficients General Test

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients				
		Chi ²	df	Sig.
Block 1	Step	17.342	2	.000
	Block	17.342	2	.000
	Model	17.342	2	.000

Cox & Snell R² and Nagelkerke R² values indicate the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables. In other words, these values reflected the model's explanatory power for the dependent variable. In addition to the Cox & Snell R² and Nagelkerke R² values, the Hosmer–Lemeshow test was used to evaluate the model's fit to the data set based on a comparison of the observed and expected values of the dependent variable (Hosmer et al., 2013). Table 6 shows a model summary with a -2 Log Likelihood value of 88.421, Cox & Snell R² value of 0.085, and Nagelkerke R² value of 0.203. This indicated that the independent variables explained approximately 8.5% of the variation in the dependent variable according to Cox & Snell and approximately 20% according to Nagelkerke ($p < .01$).

Table 6. Findings of Cox & Snell R² and Nagelkerke R²

Model Summary			
	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R ²	Nagelkerke R ²
Block 1	88.421	0.085	0.203

The Hosmer-Lemeshow test requires a significant value of $p > .05$ to accept the model as a good fit (Hosmer et al., 2013). According to the Hosmer–Lemeshow test result, the significance value of the model was $p = .843$ ($p > .05$). This result suggested that the logistic regression model fit the data well. In other words, there was no statistically significant difference between the observed values and the values predicted by the model; the model predictions were quite close to the actual values (Hosmer et al., 2013). This finding confirmed that the model adequately represented the data set.

In logistic regression analysis, a model containing only the constant term was established in the first step. This step represents the state of the independent variables before they were added to the model, i.e., the 'initial model' (constant only model). The initial model estimated the intrinsic probability of the dependent variable. The model only included the constant coefficient (β_0) and did not include the awareness and usage competence variables. Table 7 shows that the constant coefficient ($\beta_0 = 2.485$, $p < .01$) was statistically significant. The Exp(B) value is 12.000; this indicates that, prior to the inclusion of the independent variables in the model, the probability of the pre-service teachers believing they can use Web 2.0 tools effectively was approximately 12 times higher than the probability of them not believing so. To put it another way, most pre-service teachers in the initial model had a high degree of belief. However, since this model did not include independent variables that could explain the change in the dependent variable, it only showed the initial probability estimate. In the next stage of the analysis (Block 1), the awareness and competence variables were added, and the model was found to have improved significantly.

Table 7. Estimated Findings for the Initial Model (Constant Only Model)

Variables in the Equation							
		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Block 1	Constant	2.485	0.269	85.497	1	.000	12.000

The parameter estimates for the variables in the study's logistic regression model are shown in Table 8. The total scores from the ASWT and WTUCS are the independent variables in the model. When the p-values in Table 8 were examined, it was determined that both variables were statistically significant ($p < .05$). The odds ratio, which is fundamental to logistic regression analysis, is expressed by the Exp(B) value, which indicates how many times the independent variable increases the change in the dependent variable. The odds ratio is determined by the ratio of the probability of an event occurring to the chance of its non-occurrence, so comparing the likelihood of an event with its absence (Hosmer et al., 2013). Thus, by analyzing the parameter estimates in the equation, one can infer the impact of the significant independent factors on the dependent variable. Accordingly;

- Each point obtained from the ASWT increases the likelihood of belief in Web 2.0 tools by 3.2%.
- Each point obtained from the WTUCS increases the likelihood of belief in Web 2.0 tools by 2.2%.

- The negative and significant constant coefficient ($B=-3.654$, $p=.015$) indicates that pre-service teachers' results with low levels of awareness and competence are highly unlikely to believe they can use Web 2.0 tools effectively.

The cumulative effect of these relatively small coefficients becomes quite significant when the ASWT total score is 135 and the WTUCS total score is 195. For example, if the ASWT score increases by 10 points, the probability ratio is calculated as $(1.032)^{10} \approx 1.37$, which corresponds to an approximate 37% increase in probability. Similarly, a 10-point increase in the WTUCS score results in $(1.022)^{10} \approx 1.24$, meaning an approximate 24% increase in probability. Therefore, given the wide range of total scores on the scales, the small coefficients do not imply that the effects are insignificant. On the contrary, increases in awareness and competence levels significantly enhance pre-service teachers' likelihood of believing in their ability to use Web 2.0 tools effectively.

Table 8. Predicted Parameters and Significant Findings of the Model for Awareness and Competence in Using Web 2.0 Tools Related to Belief

		Variables in the Equation					95% C.I. for EXP(B)		
		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	Lower	Upper
Block 1	ASWT	.031	.014	5.104	1	.024	1.032	1.004	1.060
	WTUCS	.021	.009	5.157	1	.023	1.022	1.003	1.041
	Constant	-3.654	1.496	5.967	1	.015	.026		

Based on all these findings, the results of the hypothesis tests for the model created based on the estimation results for the variables in the equation are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Hypothesis Test Results

		Model Hypotheses of the Results	Result
H1		ASWT total scores have an impact on belief in using Web 2.0 tools.	Confirmed
H2		WTUCS total scores have an impact on belief in using Web 2.0 tools.	Confirmed

Overall, the study's findings indicate that pre-service teachers' awareness of Web 2.0 tools and their competence in using these tools are significantly related to each other and to their beliefs about using them in the classroom. As awareness and competence levels increase, so do pre-service teachers' beliefs in their ability to effectively employ Web 2.0 tools in instructional procedures.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study first revealed the relationship between pre-service teachers' competence in using Web 2.0 tools and their awareness of these tools. The results show a moderate positive relationship between the awareness of pre-service teachers who take educational technology course regarding Web 2.0 tools and their competence in using them. This result primarily indicates that pre-service teachers have a moderate level of familiarity with Web 2.0 technologies, know their features, are interested in Web 2.0 tools, and can comprehend the importance of these tools. It can be said that this awareness at the cognitive and affective levels acts as a bridge to action and increases the competence in using Web 2.0 tools. According to studies, there is a positive correlation between Web 2.0 awareness and usage skills (Gurbanova, 2024; Ünal, 2019). According to Şendağ et al. (2015) pre-service teachers had an intermediate level of competency, skills, and awareness in using Web 2.0 technologies. Redecker and Punie (2017) stated that being aware of Web 2.0 tools contributes to individuals' productivity and the development of their digital skills. As the level of awareness of Web 2.0 tools increases, it is possible to create interactive settings that allow pre-service teachers to effectively produce, share, and discuss information. The study revealed that the highest correlation was found between the 'knowledge' sub-dimension of awareness and the competence in using Web 2.0 tools. This suggests that when pre-service teachers learn about the Web 2.0 tools and their applications, their competence in utilizing them improves. The results show that, in addition to knowing Web 2.0 tools, the level of being able to interpret and evaluate the role of the tools in education within the scope of the perception sub-dimension can also improve the ability to use them. Therefore, an individual's experience with Web 2.0 tools, known as the perception process, and their pedagogical beliefs shape their usage skills. Karaca and Aktaş (2019) emphasise that in order to use Web 2.0 tools effectively, one must be knowledgeable about how applications are used for educational purposes.

Another finding of the study is that pre-service teachers' awareness of Web 2.0 tools and competence in utilizing them are significantly related to their belief that they can employ them effectively in their teaching practice. This result indicates that the variables in question are significant predictors of the belief variable regarding the application of Web 2.0 tools in the teaching process. This conclusion is consistent with the findings of the study of Aytan and Başal (2015). In their study, they applied various Web 2.0 tools to Turkish

pre-service teachers over an eight-week period and found that, at the end of the process, the pre-service teachers' perceptions of using these tools in their future lessons had increased positively. It may be inferred that as pre-service teachers' awareness and competence levels increase, so does their belief in their ability to effectively use Web 2.0 tools in teaching processes.

Kul and Çelik (2018) aimed to examine the effect of developing educational e-content with Web 2.0 applications on pre-service mathematics teachers' belief changes regarding their intention to use Web 2.0 technologies in their professional lives. The study made use of Web 2.0 tools appropriate for mathematics instruction. After learning about Web 2.0 tools, what they are used for, and how they are applied, pre-service teachers expressed a strong desire to employ them. Barriers such as lack of knowledge or skills in using Web 2.0 tools may also hinder teachers' desire to communicate and interact online for their professional development training (Drexler et al., 2008). Evidence shows that the more teachers or pre-service teachers participate in professional development programmes related to Web 2.0, the more they apply the technologies to their teaching, change the educational pedagogy for all students, and become more willing to use Web 2.0 tools (Eyüp, 2022; Wells & Lewis, 2006; Yükseltürk et al., 2017). Reisoğlu and Çebi (2020) developed a training curriculum to improve digital literacy among pre-service teachers. In this case study, pre-service teachers received training in a variety of modules, including one on digital content development. The study's findings emphasize the importance of enhancing practical learning in addition to theoretical knowledge in the digital content creation module, which includes a skill in using Web 2.0 tools. However, studies indicate that simply beginning to use Web 2.0 tools within the current educational paradigm will not create sufficient change in the nature of educational pedagogy to meet the needs of 21st-century learners. Therefore, educators require access to ongoing professional development to reshape the curriculum with greater knowledge, awareness, competence, and application of Web 2.0 elements (Hursen, 2021; Lemke et al., 2009). Tondeur et al. (2017) found that new instructors typically do not employ digital technologies to facilitate the development of critical and creative thinking skills that are essential for students in the 21st century. In this context, some studies indicate that the use of Web 2.0 applications, when supported by student-centred approaches such as problem-based learning, can have a positive impact on pre-service teachers' professional experiences (Hursen, 2021; Koehler et al., 2017; Weller, 2013). In a study in which Hursen (2021) examined the impact of problem-based learning methods supported by Web 2.0 tools on pre-service teachers' academic achievement levels and critical thinking skills, he notes that the use of Web 2.0 applications, when supported by student-centred approaches such as problem-based learning, is likely to have a positive impact on pre-service teachers' professional development. Bandura emphasized that when people are provided with the necessary skills and knowledge in coordination with professional development, their perception of efficacy will influence their decisions regarding how much effort and time to devote to the task (Bandura, 1977, 1994; Pajares, 2002). Uyulgan and Akkuzu Güven (2022), in their study investigating chemistry pre-service teachers' competence in using Web 2.0 tools and their perspectives on the use of these tools in the context of chemistry teaching, found that pre-service teachers' competence in using Web 2.0 tools was at an intermediate level and concluded that this was generally due to pre-service teachers' lack of prior experience with these tools. The study suggested that providing pre-service teachers with opportunities to use various Web 2.0 tools would help to enhance their awareness and competence regarding these applications.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Pre-service teachers' understanding of the properties and use of Web 2.0 tools will have a positive impact on their pedagogical competencies, such as their ability to select appropriate tools for specific purposes, integrate them into the learning and teaching process, and design interactive content. Therefore, pre-service teachers should be provided with opportunities to use various Web 2.0 tools during their undergraduate education. By incorporating Web 2.0 tools into learning processes, pre-service teachers should be given opportunities to participate in both content production and sharing-based learning environments.

In today's knowledge-based societies, where 21st-century skills are gaining in importance, designing learning and teaching processes in line with technology and contemporary approaches is regarded as essential for fostering lifelong learners. In this context, professional learning environments should be provided that are enriched with learning methods capable of developing higher-order thinking skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking and creative thinking through the use of Web 2.0 tools. By creating such learning environments, the development of pre-service teachers' digital literacy levels, collaboration processes, and 21st-century skills can be studied. The study examined the relationship between pre-service teachers' awareness of Web 2.0 tools and their usage skills, and the results obtained were limited to two scales. Future studies could investigate the relationships between pre-service teachers' attitudes towards these tools, their

self-efficacy and beliefs, and their usage competencies. Furthermore, classroom observations and interviews could be conducted to gain insight into pre-service teachers' application of Web 2.0 tools, monitor their development processes, and identify the challenges they encounter.

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